

Re-framing societal perception of neurodegenerative diseases for comfortable ageing

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Introduction: Different historical ways exist how societies perceive, define, name, and categorize neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs), nevertheless, age-associated progressive diseases were always a part of human experience. Today, with neuroscience progression and emerging new technologies, we understand many NDDs as an interplay of genetic susceptibility and environmental risk factors. Still, shaping health-oriented behaviours in the population is a challenge. Also, in western culture where family ties are weak, getting old and frail is not treasured, and media predominantly focus on the disease's late to terminal stages and societal burden. Thus, age-related NDDs stigma persists and NDDs are reported to be among the most feared condition. Later mentioned can be viewed as an issue of framing NDDs societal perception in some cultures. Frames are tools that are used in communication to decide which elements are selected and need a central position to present an issue as comprehensible as possible to a diversity of audiences. Moreover, framing not only contributes to defining a certain problem but also implies the existence of alternative counter-frames. In our societies, we can observe that NDDs problematizing frames are dominant in common public discourse and alternative frames are used less often. As problematizing frames related stigma can have detrimental effect on health and wellbeing of individuals, reframing and de-problematisation may be essential to achieve a positive change in perceptions and attitudes towards ageing and accompanied challenges in our society.

Content: We have designed the Pilot 7 M&M (Mind and Mouth): Social learning interventions with lifestyle adaptations for people with cognitive decline, within the vision to facilitate care services providers to design and deploy personalized, integrated care prevention and intervention measures, but also to provide the means and tools for the empowerment and enhancement of all stakeholders' health and digital literacy to further reduce health inequalities in modern communities and as support to healthy and active age-living (COMFORTage project funded by the EU, HORIZON-HLTH-2023-STAYHLTH-01-01). This pilot will take place in Slovenia and we put in the centre each individual as an expert of his/her experience. Daily habits are often made up of a chain of actions and thoughts and by focusing on small daily actions, we are co-creating the tools for health and wellbeing maintenance for individuals. The approach is based on interdisciplinary team work and combines healthcare, neuroscience, psychology, social sciences, and information communication technology (ICT) support to tackle NDDs and prevention from multiple angles. As mentioned, vulnerability to NDD is a complex

interplay of several factors and preventive actions not always work on the long-run. One of reported reason for health problems are poor lifestyle habits and the central determinant of activity behaviour consists of a number of personal factors: individuals' attitudes, skills, emotions, beliefs and knowledge. Additionally, one emerging contributing factor is oral health and impact of oral microbiota on NDDs. Accordingly, we will evaluate cognitive and physical status and oral health of people with different levels of cognitive condition and research the effect of actions aimed at improving oral hygiene, daily routine and behaviour changes. We will use modern ICT as a supportive tool with health coaching apps, and group trainings on specific pre-designed topics. As changes of routines and habits, that are processes and practices embedded in social life, are difficult, we assume that by introducing small changes in the daily environment that make specific behaviours more likely, we can induce positive changes with larger effect. The results of Pilot 7 will generate insights on the effects of wellbeing dimension on health and research the oral health and oral microbiota effects on cognition/delay of cognitive decline and wellbeing.

Discussion: The general public as well as researchers, health care professionals, carers, policy makers etc. share a set of cultural ideas, values, and expectations that shape the societal perception of NDDs. Subsequently, the relative absence of counter-frames only confirms the negative image of some diseases. Many efforts are applied to NDD preventive actions in the population, and we understand the success or comfort aging is dependent upon individual choices and behaviours. As such, it is in turn also relevant for public health. Current public health policies stress the potential of cumulative, small changes in individual behaviour to produce significant advancements in population health. However, we often assume that we intuitively know how to change behaviour, or, that if you tell people what is good for them and what they need to do to protect their health, they will do it. Greater interdisciplinarity is needed between health, social and informatics scientists in order to actively improve the lives of individuals and work on reframing prevalent NDDs images to boost preventive behaviour in the population. Also, the ICT advances offer new insights and tools to assist the transition. This way, we are contributing to comfort ageing, with research of the relation between oral, physical health and subjective wellbeing, and with enabling changes in small daily habits that might have a protective role.

Conclusions: As we are all creatures of habits, we are including simple steps for behaviour changes in everyday life of people with risk or with NDD, and developing approaches that will support people in managing oral hygiene, social and physical activity and thus support them in comfort ageing. We also tackle the ageing and age-related NDDs framing with approach that each person shall continue to live well, with an active and healthy life; staying involved in a social network; taking care of own self, educate and stay curious, and accept the individual process of ageing.

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